

Peer-Based Ethical Consultation for Qualitative Research

MANUAL

Hella von Unger, Anna Huber, Nevien Kerk

23 February 2026

Contents

1. Summary.....	2
2. Objective.....	2
3. Who this manual is for	2
4. How to use this manual.....	2
5. Possible use scenarios.....	3
6. Procedure (Step-by-step guide).....	4
Step 1. Clarify the Initial Situation 	4
Step 2. Matching – Find a Suitable Peer 	4
Step 3. Preparing the Consultation Meeting 	5
Step 4. Conducting the Consultation 	5
Step 5. Documentation and Follow-Up 	6
7. Strengths and limitations	6
8. Background	7
On the CHANGER project and the value of ethical consultation.....	7
Why adapt a tool for the social sciences and humanities?	7
Why is this tool relevant for Research Ethics Committees (RECs)?.....	8
Appendix 1: Annotated Guiding Questions for the Peer Consultation.....	9
Appendix 2: Documentation Form	14
Appendix 3: Online resources and References	15
References.....	15

1. Summary

In qualitative research in the social sciences and humanities (SSH), as well as in other evolving study designs, ethical questions often arise during the research process and can only be anticipated to a limited extent in advance. Thus, ex-ante ethics reviews face limitations. This document presents a tool for peer-based ethical consultation designed to support researchers' ethical reflexivity and to complement formal ethics review processes. It can also be used independently of such reviews.

The manual provides a step-by-step guide to establishing and conducting peer consultations and includes selected questions intended to foster ethical reflexivity and problem-solving. The tool offers flexible support that is methodologically attuned to qualitative research practices, while remaining attentive to resource constraints. It is an adaptation of the *consultative ethics review* approach (developed within the project CHANGER) (Rauhala et al. 2026) for qualitative research in SSH and is primarily geared towards the German context, although it may also be useful in other settings.

2. Objective

The objective of this tool is to facilitate peer-based ethical reflexivity in qualitative research. By providing a structured framework for dialogical peer consultation, it supports context-sensitive and methodologically appropriate reflection on ethical issues and the development of responses to emerging challenges throughout the research process.

3. Who this manual is for

The tool aims to support:

- Researchers who use qualitative methods and wish to reflect on ethical issues in dialogue with peers (“RESEARCHERS”);
- Experienced qualitative researchers who act as consultants in the peer-based ethical consultation (“PEER CONSULTANTS”);
- Research ethics committees involved in the review and advisory processes of qualitative social research (“REC”).

4. How to use this manual

RESEARCHERS:

- may follow the outlined procedure to identify a suitable peer, prepare the consultation meeting, and document the process;
- may use the annotated guiding questions (appendix 1) to support self-reflexivity in preparation for the consultation. The questions should be revised and adapted to the specific project context. The most urgent ethical issues can be communicated to the peer consultant in advance;

- should note that the consultation may also address additional issues, at the discretion of the peer consultant. The issues that the consultation ultimately focuses on are jointly identified during the conversation.

PEER CONSULTANTS:

- may read the manual to familiarize themselves with the purpose of the tool and what is expected of their role;
- may consult the annotated guiding questions (appendix 1). These are intended to support preparation for a meaningful exchange without prescribing the course of the consultation. Issues not explicitly covered may be more relevant in specific cases. The annotations provide references to further information and resources;
- will receive a written documentation of the consultation outcomes and review it for accuracy.

REC:

- may refer qualitative researchers to the manual as a means of seeking methodologically informed ethical advice from an experienced peer;
- may suggest a peer consultation as a follow-up measure to an ex-ante ethics review;
- may invite the researchers and peer consultants to share documentation of the consultation outcomes. Any such documentation is voluntary and subject to the discretion of the parties involved.

5. Possible use scenarios

No single tool fits all contexts. This tool is intended to be adapted to the specific situation in which it is applied. Across Europe, the institutional landscape for researchers and Research Ethics Committees (REC) in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) varies considerably: in some countries, ethics review is mandatory (e.g. Greece), while in others it is not (e.g. Germany). Against this background, two main use scenarios can be distinguished.

a) Peer consultation independent of a REC

Qualitative researchers who do not have access to a REC—or whose REC is not able to provide methodologically appropriate advice—may use this tool to seek and document an ethical consultation with an experienced peer. This can strengthen researchers' capacities for ethical reflexivity and demonstrate to funders, journals, or publishers that ethical issues have been addressed proactively.

While many ethical challenges emerge during or after fieldwork, some can be anticipated at the planning stage. Engaging in peer consultation early in the research process may therefore contribute to strengthening the study design. Decisions about whether formal ethics review is required, appropriate, or advisable may also be addressed during the consultation.

b) Peer consultation complementary to a REC

RECs may lack the capacity to provide ongoing and context-sensitive ethical support to qualitative researchers and may therefore refer them to this tool as a follow-up resource after an ex-ante ethics review. Qualitative researchers often participate in established peer networks (such as interpretation or methods groups) that offer methodological support. Peer-based ethical consultation can serve as an additional resource—alongside such peer networks or supervisory arrangements—to support ethical reflection and to help researchers navigate emerging ethical questions over the course of their projects.

6. Procedure (Step-by-step guide)

Step 1. Clarify the Initial Situation

Who should consider peer-based consultation?

Researchers

Are you seeking consultation to prepare for a project, funding application, or a specific research phase? Do you wish to reflect on ethical challenges with an experienced peer? Has a Research Ethics Committee (REC) suggested this tool as a follow-up to an ex-ante review?

Research Ethics Committees (REC)

Do you want to recommend or require follow-up support for a qualitative study after completing a formal ethics review? Would a peer consultation help ensure ethical soundness throughout the research process?

Step 2. Matching – Find a Suitable Peer

Researchers choose a consultant who is:

- Familiar with the methodological approach (e.g., ethnography, grounded theory, narrative interviews, videography, etc.)
- Ideally also familiar with the topic, local research context, and stakeholders (e.g., communities, participant groups, institutions)
- Experienced, trustworthy and able to offer a safe space for reflection

 Tip: Researchers ideally select a peer themselves. RECs may support this process.

Alignment with PhD supervision

If the researcher is a PhD candidate, the peer consultation should be aligned with their supervision process. In some cases, it may be beneficial to involve a peer who is not part of the formal supervision team, as this can create space for more open, less hierarchical reflection. At the same time, involving someone familiar with the project and its academic context—such as a (co-)supervisor—may enhance continuity and depth. Both options have advantages and limitations, so the choice should be guided by the specific needs and dynamics of the doctoral project.

Step 3. Preparing the Consultation Meeting

Researchers

Researchers reflect on the annotated guiding questions (appendix 1) and prepare a concise information package for the peer consultant, which may include:

- a brief written statement outlining the purpose of the consultation and the type of advice sought (e.g. general guidance at the beginning of a project or advice on a specific ethical challenge);
- basic information about the research project (with links to further information, where available);
- an indication of openness to providing additional material if needed, mindful of the limited time of peer consultants. For example, in ongoing projects involving an “ethically important moment” (Guillemin & Gillam 2024), relevant contextual material (such as excerpts from anonymised field notes or memos) may be provided;
- a copy of this manual.

Peer Consultants

Peer consultants may wish to:

- read the materials provided and review the annotated guiding questions (appendix 1) to prepare for the consultation noting any points requiring clarification, as well as areas for reflection or potential recommendations;
- consider whether additional information might be useful (e.g. on specific challenges identified by the researcher).

Step 4. Conducting the Consultation

- **Duration:** approximately 1–2 hours
- **Format:** dialogical, structured yet flexible, and confidential
- **Orientation:** you may use the guiding questions as a point of reference (appendix 1)

Focus on:

- pressing ethical challenges
- practical options and follow-up actions

Consider:

- additional sources of information and support beyond the peer consultation. Where appropriate, peer consultants may suggest reviewing relevant literature, seeking advice from key persons in the field, drawing on or establishing peer support networks that address ethical issues, or obtaining expert legal advice.

✔ Tip: Prioritize urgent issues and consider scheduling a second meeting if needed and feasible.

Step 5. Documentation and Follow-Up

Researcher

Writes a summary protocol (1–2 pages) of the consultation (see form attached).

Peer Consultant

Reviews and amends the summary if necessary.

REC (optional)

May be informed about the consultation and, if appropriate, receive a summary of key points and outcomes.

The summary should include:

- Main discussion points and ethical considerations addressed
- Agreed-upon measures or next steps

You may use the attached form for this purpose (see appendix 2).

✔ Please ensure that the **confidentiality** of study participants and **data is protected** in any documentation, especially if shared with third parties (e.g., RECs, funders, or journals). Do not include real names of study participants or detailed descriptions of persons or places.

7. Strengths and limitations

Strengths of the *Peer Consultation Tool*:

- **Promotes ethical reflexivity:** encourages researchers to reflect systematically on ethical aspects of their projects in a dialogical setting;
- **Context-sensitive:** offers flexible guidance that can be adapted to specific methodological, institutional, and field-related contexts;
- **Supports methodological integrity:** enables ethical reflection grounded in the logic of qualitative research rather than in standardised review criteria alone;
- **Complements formal ethics reviews:** provides ongoing support beyond ex-ante reviews, which is particularly valuable for studies with evolving designs;
- **Resource-efficient:** compared to consultation by an entire committee, peer consultation requires fewer institutional resources and can often be initiated more quickly.

Limitations of the *Peer Consultation Tool*:

- **Relies on available expertise:** the quality of the consultation depends on the experience and ethical sensitivity of the selected peer(s);

- **Requires time and coordination:** identifying suitable peers and organising the consultation may involve logistical effort;
- **Does not substitute for ongoing support:** the tool is not intended to replace continuous peer exchange or supervisory support throughout the research process.

 Tip:

Peer-based consultation may also be conducted in a workshop format. This can be a valuable option for research teams and for peer consultants who receive a high volume of requests. Workshop formats can make more efficient use of consultants' limited time and foster mutual peer support among researchers seeking advice. However, such formats typically require additional financial resources and institutional support, as they should not be expected to be offered on a purely voluntary basis by individual peer consultants.

8. Background

On the CHANGER project and the value of ethical consultation

The CHANGER project¹ aims to foster innovation in ethics review processes by strengthening researchers' capacities to integrate ethical reasoning into the research design and supporting research ethics committees (RECs) in responding to emerging challenges arising from new technologies and evolving research practices. It is an interdisciplinary project funded by the European Union.²

Consultative Ethics Reviews is one of several innovative tools developed in the CHANGER project (Kaiser et al. 2024). It promotes a culture of dialogue and consultation to encourage ethical reflexivity and capacity-building among researchers and academic institutions. It thus represents a fundamentally different approach to research ethics than conventional, top-down, checklist-style procedures - often perceived by researchers as a form of "ethics policing". The "consultative ethics review" is modeled on the REC of Technical University Wien, Austria (Rauhala 2025, Rauhala et al. 2026). It describes a procedure whereby a REC meets with researchers to advise them on their research project (instead of evaluating an application without dialogue). However, this is rather resource intensive and may not include the needed methodological expertise (depending on the composition of the REC). The peer-consultation tool serves a similar function: it fosters ethical advice, but—in this case—not from the entire REC, only from one person—plus, a person who is familiar with the respective qualitative methodology in SSH and ideally the field of research.

Why adapt a tool for the social sciences and humanities?

To enable meaningful transfer to specific disciplinary contexts, the tool was adapted for use in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). While these fields place a high value on ethical reflection, they have long been critical of existing ethics governance frameworks (e.g. Denzin & Giardina 2007; Israel 2015; Iphofen & Tolich 2018; Schrag 2011). Many key methodologies and research practices, especially exploratory and qualitative approaches, do not align well with

¹ <https://changer-project.eu/>

² The CHANGER project is funded by EU HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-1 (2024-2026).

standard ethics review procedures, which are primarily designed for biomedical and standardized research contexts (e.g. Bell 2014; von Unger, Dilger & Schönhuth 2016).

This creates a need for tools that are better suited to the epistemological foundations, methodological diversity, and reflexive practices of qualitative research in the social sciences and humanities. With its focus on emerging ethical questions in evolving study designs, the tool may also be useful for other methodologies, including mixed methods studies and other emerging designs.

Why is this tool relevant for Research Ethics Committees (RECs)?

Research Ethics Committees often face challenges when assessing qualitative research proposals, particularly when these appear less detailed or structured than proposals grounded in biomedical or quantitative logics. This does not reflect a lack of care or quality on the part of researchers. Rather, it stems from the open, iterative, and emergent nature of qualitative methodologies, in which key decisions are shaped in the field rather than fully specified in advance.

The *Peer Consultation Tool* supports RECs in better understanding the specificities of qualitative research and the ethical challenges it may entail. It highlights that ex-ante ethics review alone may be insufficient to ensure responsible research conduct in qualitative projects. Instead, ongoing ethical reflection—ideally through dialogue with peers who have relevant methodological expertise—is essential as the research process unfolds.

By recommending and supporting peer-based consultation formats, the tool offers a constructive response to this need. It allows RECs to refer researchers to a complementary, discipline-sensitive process for ethical support, especially in areas where the REC itself may lack in-depth methodological expertise. Thus, the tool enhances, rather than replaces, formal ethics review by helping RECs navigate complexity without overextending their mandate.

Appendix 1: Annotated Guiding Questions for the Peer Consultation

This guide provides a set of annotated questions to support ethical reflexivity and peer consultations for qualitative research. Please adjust the questions to fit the specific research project and context.

Question	What to Consider	Links and Notes
1. Is there a specific issue or concern prompting the consultation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The more clearly researchers can articulate their need for consultation, the better consultants can respond and focus the discussion on the areas where guidance is most needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarify the current state of the research (planning stage or ongoing)
2. Have necessary project and context information and materials been provided?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing background information enables the consultant to better understand the specific context in which ethical questions emerge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers may briefly present this information orally at the beginning of the consultation
3. Who is funding the research?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there any pressures from funders and potential conflicts of interest? - Is the academic freedom of researchers in any way constrained? Who could help you find a suitable compromise if ethical or professional tensions arise? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In evaluation or applied research, some funders may be reluctant to share undesirable results publicly. Researchers should therefore consider potential conflicts of interest and clarify publication and dissemination arrangements in advance.
4. Who is expected to benefit?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beyond knowledge production, does the research aim to achieve a practical or applied impact? (e.g., a benefit for the community; social justice aims) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If so, please consult the relevant literature (e.g. participatory, transdisciplinary, indigenous, decolonial approaches to research ethics)
5. What ethics guidelines or literature may be of help?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have you consulted the relevant ethics codes and guidelines of your institution, your field and discipline? - What do you learn from other studies about ethical questions, challenges and solutions? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For SSH in Germany, ethics codes can be found here: www.neks.info - Search for relevant literature addressing your field and concerns

6. Prior field experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you have sufficient prior research experience or field-specific expertise to conduct the project in a responsible fashion? - Can you collaborate with someone with such expertise? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This is particularly important when working on sensitive topics or in challenging research settings
7. Has there been advice from key persons in the field?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have you received support and feedback from stakeholders in the field? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn from ethnography and find key persons to advise you
8. Support structures: Who supports the researcher and the project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are you a member of an interpretation group? Do you have access to peer support? - Is there academic supervision and/or research supervision available? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For Germany, a list of qualitative methods peer groups can be found here: https://qualitative-forschung.de/uebersicht-forschungswerkstaetten/ - You may also consider reflection labs (von Unger et al. 2022)
9. What power dynamics and social relationships in the field are relevant? (e.g. dependencies, hierarchies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How might power inequalities shape the research process and interactions in the field? - Consider how positions of dependence, authority, or vulnerability may affect access, participation, consent, data generation, and interpretation. - This includes power asymmetries related to gender, ethnicity, age, legal status, or socioeconomic position. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Since qualitative research takes place in everyday lifeworlds—online or offline—it is embedded in existing social relations and inequalities. Ethical reflection therefore requires attention to how power asymmetries may shape the research process and affect those involved.
10. Assessing and managing risks to participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the risks associated with study participation? How will you address and reduce these? - Are any of the potential participants in a particularly vulnerable situation (e.g. due to age, disability, political, legal, or institutional conditions)? - How will you make sure that participation is voluntary? - How may research results affect the participants and their communities? - Can you involve stakeholders in the reflexive process? - How critical are you planning to be in your analysis? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential risks to participants may concern emotional, social, legal, economic, physical, or reputational aspects - Attention to vulnerability should not come at the expense of awareness of heterogeneity within groups and of participants' agency, even in challenging life situations.

11. Assessing and managing risks to researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How may the researcher be vulnerable? - How will you protect your safety? - How much personal information are you willing to share with the field? Where is the line? - Do you need a professional social media profile? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researcher vulnerability involves emotional, physical, legal, and reputational risks and extends beyond qualitative research (for guidance on protecting researcher safety, see e.g. Grimm et al., 2020; AoIR, 2025) - Reflecting on researcher vulnerability can also have analytic value (von Unger 2021, von Unger et al. 2022)
12. How is field access established?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are gatekeepers or mediators involved? - Will you use social media? - Is there a project website and an information sheet in lay language? - Is it ensured that participants are able to refuse participation without any negative consequences? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Literature on ethical aspects of social media research: Gliniecka (2023); Schlütz & Zillich (2023); Schlütz & Möhring (2025); Franzke et al. 2021
13. How and by whom is informed consent required and obtained?	<p>Individual, written consent is not always possible (e.g. in participant observation and social media research). Still: who may provide informed consent?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How is consent obtained? - In which form: oral or written? - If written (e.g. interview studies or focus groups): how? - If oral: how is it documented (e.g. field notes, postscript, recording)? - If no informed consent is planned, please explain. - How can you ensure that participants are able to say no and refuse to participate in your study? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For info on how to phrase an informed consent sheet see handouts and templates developed by RatSWD and Qualiservice (appendix 3); - In ethnographic research, informed consent is a contested concept with limited value (e.g. Bell 2014); - informed consent is also a challenge in social media research (see above)
14. What kind of data are generated?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What kind of data are you producing? (audio, video, text (e.g. fieldnotes, transcripts, social media posts), visual data, etc) - How sensitive are these data? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data production in qualitative research cannot be fully planned in advance but evolves with the research process - Different data raise varying risks related to identifiability, sensitivity, consent, storage, sharing, and re-use.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - consider appropriate data management strategies early on (appendix 3)
15. How and when will you anonymize your data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anonymization and pseudonymization are key strategies for reducing risks associated with social science data; in qualitative research, however, these must be balanced against the need to preserve the data's heuristic value. - In many qualitative studies, anonymization takes place in (at least) two rounds: initial/rough anonymization of the the raw data and more detailed measures of selected citations later 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For challenges related to anonymizing qualitative data see e.g. Bischof et al. (2022); Saunders et al. (2015); Tilley/Woodthorpe (2011); von Unger (2021); for practical advice: Qualiservice (appendix 3)
16. Data management and ownership: Are data handled, secured, and stored responsibly?	<p>In qualitative research, data management plans need to be adapted over the course of the research.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are data stored and protected? - Who will have access? - Will the data be archived or made available for reuse? (How?) - Consider the risks (e.g. de-anonymization, data misuse) and benefits (e.g. reuse, appreciation) of archiving. Involve the participants (archiving only with explicit and written informed consent) and only use professional archives for qualitative data. - Who owns the data? In participatory research, the community may own the data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the management of qualitative data, see Mozygemba et al. (2025); see also Qualiservice (Appendix 3). - Note that not all qualitative data are suitable for archiving; follow the EU-endorsed principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary." - Observe the CARE Principles when conducting research with Indigenous communities.
17. What are ethical issues during the data analysis process?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How critical is the analysis of participants, groups, or organizations? - How are academic rigor and the protection of participants balanced? - Are AI tools used in the analysis? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical analysis may pose risks of misrepresentation, stigmatization, or reputational harm. - balance analytical rigor with participants' rights to protection, including careful choices regarding anonymization and presentation. - The use of AI tools should be transparent, covered by explicit informed consent, and

		assessed with regard to data protection, confidentiality and socioecological costs.
18. How will you ensure ethical conduct in publications with regard to anonymization, representation, and member checking?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How will you anonymize the data in your final publications? - Will you make the results available to the participants or the wider community? - What potential pitfalls related to representation do you foresee, and how can you avoid misrepresenting participants or their communities? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - See above - Member checks may be valuable, but are not always feasible or appropriate, e.g. in power-critical research involving elites
19. Do you need a formal ethics review?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have you been in contact with a REC/ undergone ethics review? - Do you need to undergo an ethics review? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Even where ethics review is not legally mandated (e.g. in Germany; von Unger et al., 2016), some funders, journals or publishers may still require it.
20. What other issues or aspects are important to ensure ethical research practice?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Please add any further topics or questions you think are relevant for ethical reflection in this study context. 	

Appendix 2: Documentation Form

Documentation of a Peer-Based Ethical Consultation for Qualitative Research

Date of the consultation:

Name of researcher:

Name of consulting peer:

Main purpose of the consultation:

- Support in the planning stage of a study
- Advice on an ethical issue arising during the conduct of a study
- Other:

Main points discussed:

.....
.....
.....

Suggestions, solutions and steps forward:

.....
.....
.....

Would the consultant be willing to be available for a follow-up meeting if needed?

- Yes No Maybe

.....

Date, Signature (RESEARCHER)

.....

Date, Signature (PEER CONSULTANT)

Appendix 3: Online resources and References

CHANGER

- CHANGER project website: <https://changer-project.eu>
- CHANGER on ZENODO: https://zenodo.org/communities/changer_project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

Related Projects, Resources and Networks

- BriGRETE – Bringing the Gap in Research Ethics Training & Education: <https://www.brigrete.eu>
- Embassy of Good Science: https://embassy.science/wiki/Main_Page
- EUREC – European Network of Research Ethics Committees: <https://eurecnet.eu/>
- Fekom – Research ethics in communication and media studies: <https://www.forschungsethik-kmw.de/en/about-project>
- irecs – Understanding Ethics in Tech: <https://www.irecs.eu/>
- neks - Network of Research Ethics Committees in the Social Sciences: <https://neks.info/en>

Qualitative Research Ethics

- German Association of Social and Cultural Anthropology (DGSKA): <https://www.dgska.de/en/ethics/>
- Qualiservice (Qualitative data archive): <https://www.qualiservice.org/en/>

Research Data Management

- CARE principles for indigenous data governance: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>
- LB Unger (2025): Handout „Data management in qualitative methods training“, LMU Munich: <https://www.soziologie.lmu.de/en/chairs/chair-07/academics/qualitative-research.html>
- Mozygamba K, Gebel T, Hanekop H, Köchling S, Lösch T (2025). Forschungsdatenmanagement und Data Sharing qualitativer Daten – Eine Handreichung. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26092/elib/4334>
- RatSWD (2023) Research Data Management for Small Research Projects. A practical guide. Berlin. <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/publication/research-data-management-for-small-research-projects/>
- Responsible Open Data: <https://rosie-project.eu/>

References

- AoIR Risky Research Working Group (2025). Risky Research: An AoIR Guide to Researcher Protection and Safety. The Association of Internet Researchers (AoIR). <https://aoir.org/riskyresearchguide/> (Accessed: 19.12.25)
- Bischof S, Lengerer F, Meyer F (2022). Traces of Interaction in Digital Space: On the Tension Between Public Accessibility and Anonymity in Qualitative Research Processes. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 23(3). <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-23.3.3893> (Accessed: 01.12.25)
- Denzin NK, Giardina MD (2007). Introduction: Ethical futures in qualitative research. In NK Denzin & MD Giardina (Eds). *Ethical futures in qualitative research: Decolonizing the politics of knowledge*. Walnut Creek, CA: Left Coast Press, pp. 9–44.
- Dingwall R (2016). The Social Costs of Ethics Regulation. In Will C. van den Hoonaard & Ann Hamilton (Eds). *The ethics rupture. Exploring alternatives to formal research ethics review*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, pp. 25–42.
- Franzke AS, Muis I, Schäfer MT (2021). Data ethics decision aid (deda): A dialogical framework for ethical inquiry of AI and data projects in the Netherlands. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 23(3), 551–567. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-020-09577-5>
- Franzke AS, Bechmann A, Zimmer M, Ess C & the Association of Internet Researchers (2020). Internet Research: Ethical Guidelines 3.0. <https://aoir.org/reports/ethics3.pdf>.
- Gliniecka M (2023). The Ethics of Publicly Available Data Research: A Situated Ethics Framework for Reddit. *Social Media + Society*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231192021>.

- Grimm J et al. (2020). Safer Field Research in the Social Sciences. A Guide to Human and Digital Security in Hostile Environments. London: Sage.
- Guillemin M, Gillam L (2004). Ethics, responsibility and "ethically important moments' in research. *Qualitative Inquiry* 10(2): 261-280.
- Iphofen R, Tolich M (2018). Foundational issues in qualitative research ethics. In R Iphofen & M Tolich (Eds.) *The Sage handbook of qualitative research ethics*. London: Sage, pp. 1-18.
- Israel, M (2015). *Research ethics and integrity for social scientists: Beyond regulatory compliance*. London: Sage.
- Kaiser M, Mollaki V, Rauhala M, Marušić A, Borry P, Misfud Bonnici J, Nousias, A, Karkaletsis V (2024). Conceptual and methodological foundations for innovative changes in research ethics review - the CHANGER project. *8th World Conference on Research Integrity (WCRI)*, Athens, Greece. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16258447>
- Mozygemba K, Gebel T, Hanekop H, Köchling S, Lösch T (2025). Forschungsdatenmanagement und Data Sharing qualitativer Daten – Eine Handreichung. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26092/elib/4334>
- Rauhala M (2023). Beyond approval: experiences and lessons from constructing research ethics review *ENRIO 2025, Congress on Research Integrity Practice: Research Integrity, Power Dynamics and Safe Institutional Culture*. University of Lubljana, Slovenia. Book of Abstracts: 80.
- Rauhala M, Kaiser M, Manos I, Garani-Papadatos T, von Unger H, Berliri M, Pfister J, Giouvanopoulou K, Ziouvelou X, Mollaki V (2026). CHANGER Manual for the Method "Consultative Ethics Review" - preliminary version 1.2 - 25.05.2026. Zenodo DOI [10.5281/zenodo.18860981](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18860981)
- Saunders B, Kitzinger J, Kitzinger C (2015). Anonymising interview data: Challenges and compromise in practice. *Qualitative Research* 15 (5): 616–632.
- Schlütz D, Zillich AF (2023). Forschungsethik und wissenschaftliche Integrität: Herausforderungen und Chancen für Forschung in und mit digitalen Medien. In S Stollfuß, L Niebling, F Raczkowski (Eds.), *Handbuch Digitale Medien und Methoden*. Springer, pp. 1-18.
- Schlütz D, Möhring W (2025). Forschungsethische Aspekte und Herausforderungen von Online-Kommunikation. In W Schweiger, K Beck & V Karnowski (Eds.), *Handbuch Online-Kommunikation*. Springer VS, pp. 1-20. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-18017-1_38-1
- Schrag ZM (2011). The Case against Ethics Review in the Social Sciences. *Research Ethics*, 7(4), 120-131.
- Tilley L, Woodthorpe K (2011). Is it the end for anonymity as we know it? A critical examination of the ethical principle of anonymity in the context of 21st century demands on the qualitative researcher. *Qualitative Research* 11 (2): 197–212.
- von Unger H (2016). Reflexivity beyond Regulations. *Teaching Research Ethics and Qualitative Methods in Germany. Qualitative Inquiry* 22 (2), S. 87–98.
- von Unger H (2021). Ethical reflexivity as research practice. *Historical Social Research* 46 (2), S. 186–204. <https://doi.org/10.12759/hsr.46.2021.2.186-204>
- von Unger H, Dilger H, Schönhuth M (2016). Ethics Reviews in the Social and Cultural Sciences? A Sociological and Anthropological Contribution to the Debate [18 paragraphs]. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research* 17(3), Art. 20. <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0114-fqs1603203>.
- von Unger H, Huber A, Kühner A, Odukoya D, Reiter H (2022). Reflection Labs: A Space for Researcher Reflexivity in Participatory Collaborations. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods* 21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069221142460>

Acknowledgements

- The CHANGER project has received funding from the European Commission Horizon WIDERA under Grant Agreement No 101131683.

We thank the CHANGER consortium, the Network of Research Ethics Committees in the Social Sciences (neks) and members of the Qualitative Research Workshop at LMU Munich for their invaluable feedback during the development of the tool.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Suggested Citation:

von Unger, H., Huber, A., & Kerk, N. (2026). *Peer-Based Ethical Consultation for Qualitative Research: Manual* (Version 1.0). CHANGER Project. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.19097525